

Horizon Europe

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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General Information

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Proposal Acronym: Trans Modernismo

Full Title: Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America

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Department: Universität zu Köln. Department of Romance Studies

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Scientific Area: SOC - Social Sciences and Humanities (SOC); gender history; cultural studies; cultural diversity; literary theory and comparative literature; literary styles; women and gender studies; libraries and archives

Document: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (DCEP)

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Abstract

This document is the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plan (DCEP) of the Horizon-MSCA-2022-PF-01 (MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2022) project Trans Modernismo, proposal 101103095. This DCEP explains how this project will amplify results, highlighting the outcomes accomplished so far and the strategies for further development of goals established in the original proposal as well as new ones that emerged during the implementation of the action. A critical objective of this project is to create a positive impact across different fields of the Humanities, the Social Sciences, and Gender and Sexuality Diversity Education, including academic and non-academic audiences. I outline the open access policy, the goals, and milestones, that is, the control points in the project that chart development and progress. I also describe how the realization of significant results allowed me to continue with the next phases of the project. Each milestone reached so far will be verifiable by Internet links and digital object identifiers (DOIs) findable in Zenodo, the general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program.

Introduction

This report describes the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plan of the project Trans Modernismo of the Horizon-MSCA-2022-PF-01, Grant Agreement # 101103095. It is being completed as the project progresses and includes the explanation of all completed milestones and all documents published or created during the realization of this plan.

Unit 1 contains information of the Open Access Policy executed in the development of the DCEP provided by the European Research Council Guidelines.

Unit 2 details the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan. I specify the tools and strategies to be implemented in the years to come for the three distinctive blocs of the plan: 1) Communication; 2) Dissemination; 3) Exploitation.

Unit 3 reports the first DCE deliverables achieved associated with the research conducted during the implementation of the project in the following dates: 1/9/2023—30/6/2024. **10 months.**

Unit 4 includes a Gantt chart of the DCE plan strategies and anticipated deadlines for the deliverables proposed.

Unit 1. Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility (Article 17 GA)

Dissemination

Dissemination of results

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Additional dissemination obligations

Where the call conditions impose additional dissemination obligations, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Open Science

Open science: open access to scientific publications

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication. Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements. Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine- actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication. Only publication fees in full open access venues for scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Open science: research data management

The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- - establish a data management plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- - as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- - as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence/dedication with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP
- - provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data. Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s) and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

Open science: additional practices

Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding open science practices, the beneficiaries must also comply with those. Where the call conditions impose additional obligations regarding the validation of scientific publications, the beneficiaries must provide (digital or physical) access to data or other results needed for validation of the conclusions of scientific publications, to the extent that their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (and unless they already provided (open) access at publication). Where the call conditions impose additional open science obligations in case of a public emergency, the beneficiaries must (if requested by the granting authority) immediately deposit any research output in a trusted repository and provide open access to it under a CC BY licence, a Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. As an exception, if the access would be against the beneficiaries' legitimate interests, the beneficiaries must grant non-exclusive licenses — under fair and reasonable conditions — to legal entities that need the research output to address the public emergency and commit to rapidly and broadly exploit the resulting products and services at fair and reasonable conditions. This provision applies up to four years after the end of the action (see Data Sheet, Point 1).

Plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities Unless excluded by the call conditions, the beneficiaries must provide and regularly update a plan for the exploitation and dissemination of results including communication activities.

Source: European Research Council. URL <https://erc.europa.eu/manage-your-project/open-science>

Unit 2. Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan

A first draft of the DCE Plan is presented in this section, which will be further developed during the afterlife of the project. While dissemination focuses on making knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge for academics and civil society, communication and exploitation focuses on citizens, the media, researchers, and general educators. I am envisioning this plan taking into consideration that my new home institution, The University of Chicago as per July 2024, is located in the United States but many of the following initiatives will be implemented having in mind European academic and non-academic sectors.

TRANS MODERNISMO	PROJECTS FOR DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION & EXPLOITATION	PLATFORMS FOR DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION & EXPLOITATION	METHODS FOR DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION & EXPLOITATION
WHAT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Website: The Queer Ancestries Digital Humanities Project. 2. Social Media Platforms to Inform on Preliminary and Final Results 3. Flyers and Downloadable Presentations/Small Catalogues to be Published in Website 4. Press Articles 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Academic presentations 2. Lectures and workshops in congresses and academic and non-academic gatherings 3. Peer-reviewed articles 4. Monograph 5. Data Sets 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. University Courses: Lectures and training sessions in university classrooms. 2. Collaboration. Collaborative Work with students, librarians, and experts in initiatives for the study of the humanities
WHERE	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Internet 2. Congresses 3. European Commission Tools for DCE Initiatives: 1. Horizon Magazine 2. Open Research Europe 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open Access Peer-Reviewed Journals 2. International Congresses 3. University Events 4. University Museums 5. Cultural Institutes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal Courses and Seminars at University 2. Congresses 3. Invited Talks 4. Work Groups
TO WHOM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. European Citizens 2. Global Citizens 3. European and Global LGBTQ Institutions 4. Diversity Education Sectors 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Global Academic Community 2. Diversity Educators 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Humanities & Social Sciences Students 2. Humanities & Social Sciences Researchers

Table 1: Overview of the Trans Modernismo DCE Plan

Project Description

Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America analyzes the emergence of a new gender expression in early-twentieth-century Latin American literature, medical science, and visual culture: the «marimacho». In the Hispanic tradition, marimacho is the umbrella notion that may refer to a sexist slur as much as a modern form of non-binary gender, a transmasculine identification, or a lesbian identity. This project examines the aesthetic construction of this hybrid, counter-cultural, and gender-dissident figure in an extensive cultural repertoire that includes novels, plays, films, leaflets, medical studies, prison and mental hospital records, poems, newspaper, and tabloid articles. The research draws upon multiple theoretical schools and philosophical resources from gender and sexuality studies, especially queer theory.

Queer scholarship addresses not only the political self-representation of LGBTQ bodies. Queer studies also examine major problems in minority discourse: the medical stigmas around homosexuality and transness, the non-normative/non-reproductive uses of erotic pleasures, and the broad implications of 'gender dysphoria' for orthodox notions of citizenship. In this sense, I examine the specificity of practices carried out by a rich plethora of fin-de-siècle Latin American female and trans*masculine subcultures as well as some figures of male queerness: uranistas and maricas (homosexuals) soldaderas (women soldiers), llaneras and linyeras (rural and transient women), cuchilleras (knife fighters), arrabaleras (tango singers), bolleras (tomboys), safistas and invertidas (lesbian & trans* masculine identities), vampiras (criollo vernacular for hysterics), and other gender-dissident figures of the turn of the century. My analysis of the chosen corpus will demonstrate how queer men, lesbians and trans*men contested misogynist and sexual slurs by showing how gender and sexual orientation, far from being natural, are both constructed through performance and the adoption of diverse prosthetic artifacts, from hair and clothing to makeup and other cosmetics.

I seek to increase the understanding of the region's politics of gender and sexuality during the modernizing era (1880s-1930s), that is, before the solidification of LGBTQ activism, pride literature, and minority social movements of the global 1960s. In response to the new gender dynamics led by fin-de-siècle cosmopolitan networks of first-wave feminism and secret homosexual fraternities, the keepers of gender normativity created the marimacho as a monstrous version of conventional masculinity. The main objective of this research is to investigate why a broad range of cultural materials named queer men and women, non-binary individuals, and trans* men as marimachos, as gender hackers that put at stake the Latin American futures of heteronormativity, reproduction, and family life.

Commitment for Diversity Research and Education:

This project is committed to a transformative scholarly framework that validates the cultural memory of stigmatized Latin American and European gender and sexual minorities, especially European queer migrants to South America. It seeks to recognize and give visibility to the epistemic, cultural, and institutional violence historically endured by the LGBTQ community. This project addresses the late nineteenth- and early twentieth-century legacies of homophobia, transphobia, and misogyny recorded in the literary and scientific archives of the region, with a global perspective. In my combination of literary criticism, historical work, archival research, and the critique of past sexual and medical taxonomies, I read against the grain of the original violence that represented LGBTQ peoples as abject subjects unworthy of full citizenship in the cultural production of the period 1880-1930. My research will be an opportunity to challenge official narratives about gender and sexual minorities. A principal goal of my research is to expand the cultural history of queer Latino collectives. The attention to queer cultural memory will acknowledge the historical stigmatization of LGBTQ peoples persecuted by state power and endured confinement in prisons and mental

hospitals in the early twentieth century. Ultimately, this is a research project that seeks historical restitution for past Latin American LGBTQ collectives.

Dissemination Objectives

Short term—1-2 years

- **Academic Publication:** Publish the research findings in reputable Open Access peer-reviewed journals specializing in Latin American history, comparative literature, gender and sexuality studies, and cultural studies to ensure academic rigor and recognition. (1) A monograph to be submitted possibly to the National University of La Plata Press. Originally, in my proposal, I proposed the University of Toronto Press. But since this press is not open access, I would consider the prestigious open access press Universidad Nacional de La Plata, one of the most important and recognized open repositories in the world: <https://www.editorial.unlp.edu.ar/genero>. This monograph is a long-term project that will extend the period of the tenure of my MSCA fellowship. (2) Three single-authored articles to be submitted to the open access journals possibly a) *Bulletin of Spanish Studies*, *Latin American Research Review* and *Journal of Homosexuality* b) Others considered: *Anclajes* (Universidad de La Pampa, Argentina) and *Genre, Sexualité & Société* (Centre national de la recherche scientifique, France). These articles will analyze the following topics: (a) the medicalized depiction of male queerness, trans*masculine expression and transvestism in literature; (b) the types of transgender affirmation that novelists, doctors, and playwrights condemned as ‘sexual inversion’ and crimes ‘against morality’; and (c) the role of disciplines such as endocrinology, psychiatry, legal medicine, and criminology in the making of the *marimacho*, a ‘monster gender’, a somatic construction that helped to solidify the *cishetero* scientific notion of ‘gender dysphoria.’
- **Conference Presentations:** Present the research at international and regional conferences related to Latin American studies, gender studies, and history to engage with colleagues and receive feedback. In 2025, I will attend the LASA San Francisco Conference. <https://lasaweb.org/en/lasa2024/upcoming-congresses/>. Other conferences are being considered, such as the 2025 Annual Meeting of the American Comparative Literature Association, which will be held virtually, May 29 - June 1, 2025. <https://www.acla.org/annual-meeting>.
- **Collaboration with Cultural Institutions:** Partner with cultural centers to organize exhibitions, lectures, and discussions that highlight the research findings and their contemporary relevance. The first institution to contact will be the Chicago Center Halsted to plan a lecture series as part of my third mission commitment. <https://www.centeronhalsted.org>.
- **Educational Materials:** Create and distribute educational materials, such as lesson plans, multimedia presentations, and articles, for use in university courses to integrate my research into curricula. To be shared in Zenodo. See here first result: Halaburda, C. G. (2024, May 30). Programa de seminario avanzado. América Latina LGBTQ: escenas de la literatura, la ciencia y la cultura visual en contexto global (s XIX-XX-XXI). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395388>.

Long term—1-4 years

- **Digital Presence:** Establish a dedicated website to share research updates, summaries of findings, and downloadable resources, making the research accessible to a broader audience. This website will be a collaborative enterprise among colleagues from Europe, the United States, and Latin America. But especially will be a platform where my students will contribute with blog entries, translations of 19th century queer materials (copyright free), and digital illustrations. The objective is to create a website with multiple kinds of engagements. A preliminary plan is deployed in the annex of this document.
- **Media Engagement:** Write op-eds, participate in interviews, and collaborate with journalists to disseminate the research through newspapers, magazines, and online media platforms, reaching a wider audience. A preliminary plan is deployed in the annex of this document.

- **Community Engagement:** Work with LGBTQ+ and women's rights organizations in Latin America to share findings and support advocacy efforts, ensuring the research has a direct impact on ongoing social justice movements. I have experience carrying out these initiatives. I gave lectures in the past with the Centro Ayelén in Tucumán, Argentina in 2022.
- **Public Outreach:** Develop public lectures and workshops aimed at educating the general public and non-academic audiences about the findings to increase awareness of the historical roots of homophobia and misogyny in the context of the Global South. I began this initiative in Cologne in the Center Machado during the implementation of my project. I gave a public lecture on 10/04/2024. Find information here: <http://spanischer-verein.com/?p=5957>

Communication Objectives

Long term—1-5 years

Policy Influence: Advocate for policy changes or educational reforms based on the research findings by engaging with policymakers and educational authorities. Provide evidence-based recommendations to support initiatives aimed at addressing contemporary issues of misogyny, homophobia, and lesbophobia in Latin America, the United States, and Europe. I began by contacting the Argentine consul in the city of Bonn to organize an event for PRIDE month. The consul visited my lecture in the Center Machado on April 10, 2024 and we began conversations on possible collaborations in the future for official events but also for possible contacts with officials to inform on the importance of diversity education.

Exploitation Objectives and Initiatives

Long term—1-5 years

My long-term plan for exploitation includes mainly to adapt my academic research on the history of queerness in Latin America to digital humanities initiatives so I can make it more accessible, engaging, and interactive for multiple publics. This initiative will also be open access and will be available in Zenodo. Across different mediums and with the help and collaboration of students and experts of the Center for Digital Scholarship (CDS) of the University of Chicago (<https://digitalhumanities.uchicago.edu/project/center-for-digital-scholarship/>), I would like to pursue the following ideas that will give shape to the bigger project, the website The Queer Ancestries Digital Humanities Project.

Interactive Maps

1. **Historical Timelines and Geolocations:** Create interactive maps showing significant events, places, and figures in the history of homosexuality in Latin America and Europe. Some examples are the Ball of 41 in Mexico (1901), the visit of Josephine Baker to Buenos Aires (1929), and the publication of *La Garçonne* [La Marimacho] (1922) by Victor Margueritte in Buenos Aires and Latin America. Each location can have pop-up information, images, and links to primary sources or further readings. These geolocations will also be connected with my data set so scholars and the general public can access the reference data with relevant information on these historical and cultural events.
2. **Migration and Cultural Exchange:** Map out the migration patterns of LGBTQ+ individuals and communities, highlighting how cultural exchanges influenced LGBTQ+ identities and movements in the 19th

century. Examples in my research are the Spanish travesties that migrated from Madrid to Buenos Aires in the late 1800s. I would engage students to contribute in this section of the website.

Infographics

1. Historical Timelines: Design infographics that visually represent key events, legal changes, and societal shifts regarding homosexuality in Latin America. These infographics will be available in Zenodo.
2. Cultural Impact: Develop infographics showing the influence of LGBTQ+ individuals and movements on Latin American and European culture, politics, and art. These infographics would have minimal information but would be visually impactful with QR codes leading to my data set for scholars and the public to find out more about the project.

Story Maps

1. Personal Stories: Use platforms like Esri Story Maps to combine maps, text, images, and videos to tell personal stories of LGBTQ+ individuals throughout history. These Story Maps would feature stories of queer women or queer characters related to my research and educational materials. I would consider founding a network of students and colleagues to contribute to this initiative. The StoryMap would feature a 3-5 minute video featuring a queer novel, a queer theatre play, or a song related to Trans Modernismo and would include a bibliography and a link to queer archives, such as the Schwule Museum Library of Berlin or the Ibero-Amerikanisches Institute of Berlin for the audience to keep the engagement.

Web Series in YouTube Channel and Available in Zenodo.

1. Educational Web Series: Develop a web series aimed at educating a broader audience about the history and struggles of LGBTQ+ individuals in Latin America and Europe and also Queer Literature. 30 minutes lectures led by me with content related to Trans Modernismo.

By utilizing these digital humanities approaches, I will bring my research to a wider audience, foster greater understanding and engagement, and preserve important historical narratives for future generations. *These objectives and initiatives will help ensure that the research not only contributes to academic knowledge but also has a meaningful impact on public understanding of queer history.*

Note on the future of the project beyond termination: As indicated in the amendment, these initiatives will be developed under a new institutional affiliation as of July 1st, 2024. I will be a Tenure-Track Assistant Professor of Latin American Studies: Department of Romance Languages and Literatures, University of Chicago. However, as indicated in article 17 of the GA, I will attend at my obligations to keep the principles of open science and successfully implement the DCE plan.

Note on Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation milestones.

In the very initial phase of the project, dissemination has focused on presenting in conferences, invited talks, and workshops as well as sharing data sets in the respective repository (Zenodo). Sharing the first results was aimed at raising awareness among scholars and the general public. Following the generation of more extensive research results in the years to come in the shape of publications and the other initiatives outlined above, communication, dissemination, and exploitation will keep focusing on the academic community and civil society.

Unit 3. First DCE deliverables ACHIEVED associated with the research conducted during the implementation of the project in the following dates: 1/9/2023—30/6/2024. 10 months.

1. **University Courses: Lectures and training sessions in university classrooms. See Program of Study for Curricular Innovation in Queer Studies implemented at the University of Cologne, Winter Semester 2023-2024:**

- Halaburda, C. G. (2024, May 30). Programa de seminario avanzado. América Latina LGBTQ: escenas de la literatura, la ciencia y la cultura visual en contexto global (s XIX-XX-XXI). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11395388>

Academic presentations; Lectures and workshops in congresses and academic and non-academic gatherings:

- 15/11/2023. 10am. The University of Leeds, Centre for Interdisciplinary Gender Studies. A Sentimental Disability. See details and the lecture here: University of Leeds, Simonetto, P., & Halaburda, C. G. (2023, November 16). A Sentimental Disability: Queer Melodrama, Gender Deviance, and Crip Bodies in 20th Century Argentine Theatre. A Sentimental Disability: Queer Melodrama, Gender Deviance, and Crip Bodies in 20th Century Argentine Theatre, University of Leeds. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11388057>
- 15/11/2023. 17hs. The University of Manchester. Centre for Latin American and Caribbean Studies. A Cosmopolitan Uranism. See details here: <https://events.manchester.ac.uk/event/event:k25x-lnxek6jr-adurag/carlos-halaburda-university-of-cologne-a-cosmopolitan-uranism-queer-networks-of-scandal-in-the-global-nineteenth-century>
- 28/11/2023. 12hs. The University of Cologne. The Global South Studies Center. The Garçonne Scandal. See details here: <https://gssc.uni-koeln.de/veranstaltungen/gssc-seminar-reihe/gs-23-11-28-halaburda>
- Presentation at the Modern Language Association Convention 2024. Philadelphia, USA. from 4 to 7 January. “Eugenics Scripted: Reading Disability in the Ibero-Amerikanisches Institut Theatre Archive,” Carlos Gustavo Halaburda (U of Cologne). <https://www.k-saa.org/blog/romanticism-and-related-panels-at-mla-24>
- 10.1.2024. Presentation at the University of Chicago. *Argentina’s Villainous Reproduction: Melodrama and the Making of Queerness and Disability in the Age of Eugenics*. USA. 10/1/2024. <https://voices.uchicago.edu/latinamericancarib/>
- 15.3.2024. Amor, Literatura y Diversidad con Carlos Halaburda. March 15, 2024. Miércoles 10 de Abril 2024 a las 20 h in Antonio Machado Center of Cologne. <https://spanischer-verein.com/?p=5957>

- 12.6.2024—15.6.2024. The Latin American Studies Association Congress, Bogotá, Colombia. June 12-15. Online. Program: <https://lasaweb.org/en/lasa2024/final-program>

Main Activities:

1.	presented the paper Una lágrima para el atorrante: Capacitismo finisecular, sentimentalismo crip y el flâneur orillero in the Panel entitled Moda, alimentación, imagen: Estéticas higienistas del cuerpo finisecular - Parte 1
2.	participated in the Workshop entitled 'Drag Kings: Arqueología crítica de masculinidades espectaculares en Latinx América
3.	served as Session Organizer for the Workshop entitled 'Preconferencia de la sección Siglo XIX de LASA
4.	served as Session Organizer for the LASA Section Panel entitled 'Magic, Science, Spectacle: Exhibition and Knowledge in Nineteenth-Century Popular Venues
5.	served as Session Organizer for the Panel entitled 'Moda, alimentación, imagen: Estéticas higienistas del cuerpo finisecular - Parte 1
6.	served as Session Organizer for the Panel entitled 'Moda, alimentación, imagen: Estéticas higienistas del cuerpo finisecular - Parte 2
7.	served as Session Organizer for the LASA Intersection Panel entitled 'Los desafíos del archivo efímero en América Latina
8.	served as Chair for the LASA Section Panel entitled 'LGBTQ Fin de Siècle in Latin America
9.	served as Chair for the Roundtable entitled 'Crime Fiction from North to South: The Latin American Noir Revisited

Publication of Data Set:

This data set accounts for the completion of Work Packages 1 and 2: WP I. Review / Bibliography of Modernist Latin American LGBTQ Literature & Culture (months 1-5); WP II Data collection, field work, and writing (months 1-10).

This document includes the abstracts and the primary and secondary source bibliography for the five essays that will be published in open access peer-reviewed journals in English and then in a monograph in Spanish. This milestone is a key indicator of the successful development and implementation of the research plan originally presented to the MSCA Call 2022. See the document available here: Halaburda, C. G., Schulze, P. W., & University of Cologne. (2024). Birth of the Marimacho: Modernismo's Trans* Cultural Productions in Latin America [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>

Unit 4. Gantt chart of the DCE plan strategies and anticipated deadlines for the deliverables proposed in the next 4 years.

In what follows, I break down the project timeline into manageable yearly segments, allowing for regular milestones and monitoring of the plan. Here's an example of how the initiatives will be spread across the following years:

2024

1. Website Design with assistance of my new institutional affiliation, The University of Chicago
2. Initiate collaboration with students, librarians, and experts of Universities of the American Midwest (Northwestern, The University of Illinois Chicago (UIC), The University of Notre Dame, DePaul University).
3. Continue collaboration with colleagues from European Universities and Institutes with which I initiated contact while I implemented the MSCA:

- University of Cologne,
- Ruhr University,
- University of Leeds,
- University of Manchester,
- The Paris Center of the University of Chicago,
- Sorbonne University

The first initiative will be to organize an invited talk with Dr Patricio Simonetto (MSCA Alumni and Lecturer at University of Leeds) to present his book *A Body of One's Own: A Trans History of Argentina* in the Center for the Study of Gender and Sexuality, University of Chicago.

4. Academic publication: submit article **A Cosmopolitan Scandal: Homosexuality's Sensorial Transgressions in Global Nineteenth Century Forensic Literature**. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>. To be submitted October 2024 to *Journal of Homosexuality* (Open Access). <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/wjhm20>
5. Academic Publication: write article **Buenos Aires' Machona Affair: French Queerness and the Reception of Victor Margueritte's La Garçonne in 1920s Argentina**. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>.
6. New course: Queerness and Disability in the Latin American Belle Époque
7. New course: Sex, Crime, and Horror in Modern Argentine Literature

2025

1. Launch the website The Queer Ancestries Digital Humanities Project
2. Design flyers and downloadable content for educational purposes such as small lesson plans and reading guides. This task will be carried out with collaboration of students and colleagues.

3. Academic Publication: submit article **Buenos Aires' Machona Affair**: French Queerness and the Reception of Victor Margueritte's *La Garçonne* in 1920s Argentina. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>. To be submitted March 2025 to Latin American Research Review (Open Access). <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/latin-american-research-review>
4. Academic publication: Write and submit **Buenos Aires' Androgynous Panther**: Josephine Baker and the Spectacle of Racialized Queerness in the first semester. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>. To be submitted December 2025. Bulletin of Spanish Studies (Open Access). <https://www.tandfonline.com/journals/cbhs20>
5. Launch social media platforms and begin regular posting. Possible contents: new archival source findings, translation of short literary excerpts, etc. Publish initial flyers and downloadable content such as infographics with preliminary results of published research, podcasts, reading guides, etc.
6. Submit the first press article for Horizon Magazine.
7. Evaluate and update the website based on feedback.
8. New Course: Queer Capitals: Cities, Literature, Power in Global Context
9. New Course: Gender and Sexuality in Colonial Latin American Literature
10. Present paper at LASA 2025 San Francisco <https://lasaweb.org/en/lasa2024/upcoming-congresses/> at LASA 2025. <https://lasaweb.org/en/lasa2024/upcoming-congresses/>
11. Submit a press articles. Possible news platforms: *Página 12*, *The New Yorker*, *Washington Post*, *Libération*, *DW* (Deutsche Welle).

2026-2027

1. Write **A Marimacho Underworld**: Tramps, Prostitutes, and Malevas in Buenos Aires Print Culture, 1890-1930. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>
2. Write **The Marimacho Wars**: The New Woman and the Twilight of Gender Normativity in the Hispanic Press. See article description and critical bibliography here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11384482>
3. Start planning for academic presentation for the LASA Conference in Paris 2026.
4. New Course: Queer Underworlds in Global Slum Fictions
5. New Course: Global Belle Époque: Gender, Power, Empire
6. Submit book proposal to University of La Plata Press to publish a monograph based on the 3 articles published and the 2 chapters written for a monograph in Spanish for a Hispanic community. The book will be Open Access just as the articles.

